

A Comparative Study of Security-Insecurity, Risk-taking Behavior and Educational Aspiration among Traditional and Non-Traditional Occupational Groups

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The present study aims to examine the influence of selected psychological factors on vocational preference among traditional and non-traditional respondents. In the rapidly changing socio-economic environment, youth are increasingly shifting from conventional occupations toward modern and non-traditional career options such as entrepreneurship, digital professions, freelancing, and innovative vocational fields. The purpose of the present study was to investigate psychological factors influencing the preference for traditional and non-traditional vocations among youth. The Psychological factors undertaken in this investigation were Security-Insecurity, Risk-Taking and Educational Aspiration. Here, these Psychological factors were treated as independent variables and preference for traditional and non-traditional vocations was the dependent variable. For measuring these psychological factors (variables) standardized Psychological scales were used, such as Tiwari and Singh (APRC, 1975) S-I Inventory; Anwar Yousuf (APRC, 1976). Behaviour Prediction Scale (BPS) and Saxena's (APRC, 1984) Educational Aspiration Scale. The sample will consist of traditional ($N=50$) and non-traditional respondents ($N=50$) selected through purposive sampling techniques. To find out the results, descriptive statistics and t-test were used, which indicate that two groups, i.e., Traditional and Non-Traditional group differ significantly with Security-Insecurity, Risk-Taking and Educational Aspiration. The sample will. Non-Traditional Respondents scored higher on security measures, risk-taking and educational aspiration.

Keywords: Security-insecurity, risk-taking behaviour, educational aspiration, traditional vocation

Since independence, job facilities in public and private sectors grown arithmetically, whereas population and job aspirants in the public sector and private sectors have grown geometrically. It resulted different phases of unemployment in our country. Jobs aspirant youths were forced to select self-employment /job for their livelihood on one side and on the other, some were engaged themselves by preferring their own establishment/organization as traditional and non-traditional vocations according to their psychosocial constraints. Such persons were known literally as 'Entrepreneurs (Schumpeter, 1934; McClelland, 1961). The definition of 'entrepreneur' and 'entrepreneurship' was not easy to convey, The basic concept of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship was rapidly changed on account of the changing behaviour of the entrepreneur. The essence of the entrepreneur is that he can react to changing circumstances and cope with all the activities required to establish and run profitably their commercial venture, undertaking or business.

Today, a successful entrepreneur possesses the following essential virtues and qualities, human skills, legal skills, funds mobilizing skills, innovative skills, technical skills, behavioural or liaison skills, and the art of handling the existing government. Thus, the entrepreneurs are the men of skills, experience, and expertise (Hagen, 1962; Pareek & Rao, 1971).

Certain factors influence the development, progress and growth of

entrepreneurship in the country. These influencing factors are profit, motive, social climate, better location, financial incentives, right type training, follow-up support, explosion of technological and innovative knowledge, risk-bearing spirit and capacity, age, education, family environment, caste category, experience and the likes. Traditional and non-traditional entrepreneurs differ from each other in terms of different personality characteristics (Pareek & Rao, 1971).

However, this changeover is often associated with important psychological characteristics, including insecurity, risk-taking behaviour, and educational aspiration (Atkinson, 1964; Sharma, 1985). The study seeks to compare traditional and non-traditional respondents on these psychological dimensions and to understand how these variables contribute to vocational preference.

Risk-Taking

The concept originated Knight (1921), and was developed by the work of Shackle (1959), Hart (1940), and others in the field of economics, and in the field of Psychology by Edward (1964), Kogan and Wallach (1974).

In starting any job/vocation, there existed some challenges of making a decision that involved a moderate probability of success or failure, where a person's thought that his/her efforts can influence the success. They do not like to undertake tasks that are either very easy to accomplish or, on the other extreme, which are impossible to achieve. They do not tend to like situations where the outcome of a pursuit depends on chance and not on their efforts. They like to influence the outcome of their pursuit by making more efforts and having a sense of accomplishment. Psychologists have paid much attention to this variable because of its increasing importance in vocational and entrepreneurial training (McClelland, 1966-1979).

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Level of Aspiration (Educational)

The concept of level of aspiration was introduced by Demho (1941) with reference to the degree of difficulty of the goal towards which a person is striving. It is the goal-setting behavior that occurs within the range of difficulty for the individuals. It reflects an individual's ambitions in a dynamic situation. Frank (1945) defines it as the level of future performance in a familiar task, which an individual, knowing his past performance in a task, explicitly undertakes to reach. Flugel (1955) explained it in a Freudian way and according to him, setting up the goals depends upon the distance between the real self and the ego ideal.

Security-insecurity

Security - Insecurity is also an important variable of the present research work and so this phenomenon needs some clarification. Chaplin (1985) has defined the term 'Security' as the state of feeling safe and non-apprehensive about the future satisfaction of one's needs. Similarly, he has defined the term 'insecurity' as the feeling of being unable to cope, feeling unsafe,

Reberts (1984) has defined the term 'Security' in the manner undertaken by Chaplin. He said, "Security is a sense of confidence, safety, freedom from fear or anxiety, particularly with respect to fulfilling one's present (and future) needs; and the 'insecurity' is a lack of assurance, uncertainty, unprotectedness". The study of security/insecurity seems significant as a factor of personality which directly or indirectly related to the nature of entrepreneurship or vocation.

Review of Literature

On the basis of the reviewed risk-taking has been included in this study along with educational aspiration and security-insecurity of respondents, traditional and non-traditional. It has been found that non-traditional entrepreneurs have greater risk-taking behaviour as compared to their traditional counterparts under similar conditions (McClelland, 1971). Devasenapathy (1990) and Rotter (1966) found that successful entrepreneurs have a higher level of risk-taking tendency and vice-versa. Previous findings by Sinha (1980) stated that social insecurity and cultural expectations significantly affect occupational decision-making in Indian society. Traditional occupations were often associated with security and social approval, whereas non-traditional occupations involved greater uncertainty and psychological conflict. McClelland (1971) and Hundal (1981), in their studies on business entrepreneurs, found that a higher level of aspiration was associated with fast growth. The social psychological characteristics of achievement situations and determinants of behaviour are related to entrepreneurs' aspirational levels. Krishna (1986) has found that the level of aspiration contributes positively to job satisfaction. It has also been found that non-traditional entrepreneurs have a higher level of aspiration than their traditional counterparts. Pareek and Rao (1971) emphasized the role of motivational and psychological variables in occupational development. Research findings by Mangal (2007) indicated that educational aspiration positively influences achievement motivation and career advancement among students.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the security and insecurity level of the respondents who belonged to traditional and non-traditional vocations.

- To ascertain the risk-taking behavior of the respondents who belonged to traditional and non-traditional vocations.
- To examine the educational aspirations of the respondents who belonged to traditional and non-traditional vocations.

Hypotheses of the Study

On the basis of the above discussions and literature review, several hypotheses could be generated of them. Some major hypotheses have been formulated.

- The level of insecurity will be found to be greater in non-traditional respondents than in their traditional counterparts.
- Risk-taking traits of personality will be found significantly greater among non-traditional entrepreneurs than their traditional counterparts.
- The mean scores of educational aspiration will be higher among non-traditional respondents to that of their traditional counterparts.

Method

Participants

A sample consists of 100 (50 traditional & 50 non-traditional) respondents. The sample selection was based on incidental-cum-purposive. Statistical analysis of data obtained was based on t-tests.

Measures

The tools used were standardized psychological scales *S-I Inventory by Tiwari and Singh (APRC, 1975)*: designed to measure social insight, with reported reliability $\alpha \geq 0.70$.

Behaviour Prediction Scale (BPS) by Yousuf (APRC, 1976): developed to assess behavioral tendencies, showing reliability $\alpha > 0.70$.

Educational Aspiration Scale by Saxena (APRC, 1984): intended to evaluate academic goals and achievement motivation, with reliability coefficients in the $\alpha = 0.75-0.85$ range.

Results

Comparison of respondents (traditional & non-traditional) on Insecurity scores:

Data obtained on Security-Insecurity Scale were analyzed for the significance of mean-difference and the t-test was computed. Findings were displayed in the following table-

Table 1

Mean, S.D. and t-values of Traditional and Non-traditional Respondents on Security-Insecurity Scores

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	t	df	p
Traditional	50	64.25	8.87	.63	10.71	98	<.01
Non-traditional	50	74.53	10.15	.72			

An inspection of Table 1 above revealed that respondents of traditional and non-traditional vocations differed significantly on insecurity scores. Non-traditional respondents had greater mean scores ($X=74.53$) than their traditional counterparts ($X=64.25$). The

natural too, because traditional jobs were established jobs from their at least parental position, whereas non-traditional ones were new and started by the respondents, which had more market risks of success/failure on their way to handle without having much experience.

Comparison of Risk-taking Behavior on Traditional and Non-traditional Vocations

Scores obtained by traditional and non-traditional respondents on risk-taking behavior were analyzed for the significance of mean-difference and the findings were displayed in the following Table 2.

Table 2

Mean, S.D. and t-value of Traditional and Non-traditional Respondents on Risk Taking

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	t	df	p
Traditional	50	60.15	8.25	.58	9.05	98	0.1
Non-traditional	50	68.30	9.72	.69			

Observing Table 2, it was found that non-traditional job respondents perceived/reported more risk (Mean =68.30) than that of traditional job respondents (Mean=60.15). The obtained t-value (t=9.05) was found significant at .01 level of confidence. Thus, results showed that non-traditional respondents had a higher risk in comparison to traditional respondents. This is because of well-established jobs and market experience of traditional respondents, whereas non-traditional respondents had no such benefits of either established or much market experience. Hence, they perceived more risk in their comparatively new established vocation.

Educational Aspiration of Traditional and Non-Traditional Respondents

The investigator also tried to analyze the scores of educational aspiration of traditional and non-traditional respondents on a t-test. The details of observation were displayed in the following Table 3.

Table 3

Mean, S.D. and t-values of Traditional and Non-traditional Respondents on Educational Aspiration Scores

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	t	df	p
Traditional	50	42.55	8.18	.58	8.64	98	<.01
Non-traditional	50	50.67	10.37	.73			

The findings contained in Table 3 showed a significant mean difference between traditional and non-traditional respondents on the level of educational aspiration. Non-traditional respondents had a greater mean score (Mean=50.67) in comparison to the mean scores (Mean= 42.55) of traditional respondents on educational aspiration and the obtained t-ratio (t=8.64) was highly significant. This showed that respondents who belonged to non-traditional jobs had higher educational aspirations in comparison to respondents who belonged to traditional jobs.

Conclusion and Implications of the Study

Results indicate that vocational preferences are closely related to psychological factors. The respondents belonging to non-traditional vocational groups were found to have higher insecurity, higher risk-taking behaviour, and higher educational aspiration than traditional

respondents. This may be because of uncertain career conditions, unstable income opportunities, and social pressure connected with modern and unconventional occupations. Unlike traditional occupations, non-traditional careers do not provide fixed security and stability. Due to this, youth may feel more tension and doubt about their future. At this point in the period, this insecurity may inspire them to work harder, become more creative, and achieve success. The study also found that non-traditional respondents have greater risk-taking behaviour. It may be because current occupations require confidence, innovation, independence, and the ability to face challenges. Youth choosing non-traditional vocations are generally more ready to accept uncertainty and discover new opportunities. These findings support the views of David McClelland and Julian Rotter, who explained that achievement-oriented individuals are more willing to take risks.

Similarly, educational aspiration was found to be higher among non-traditional respondents. Modern vocational fields always require higher education, practical knowledge, professional skills, and continuous learning. Therefore, individuals interested in such occupations usually develop higher educational goals and ambitions. These findings are supported by the theories of Abraham Maslow and Donald Super, who highlighted the importance of self-development, aspiration, and future planning in vocational behaviour.

Overall, the findings suggest that non-traditional respondents are more ambitious, future-oriented, adaptable, and willing to face challenges compared to traditional respondents.

The study concludes that psychological factors play an important role in vocational preference among youth. Non-traditional respondents were found to have higher insecurity, greater risk-taking behaviour, and stronger educational aspiration than traditional respondents.

The results indicate that changing vocational patterns in modern society are closely linked with psychological characteristics. Youth picking non-traditional vocations seem ready to change, innovate, and pursue personal progression, while they may also experience greater uncertainty and pressure.

The present study provides a sound stepping stone for further study. The findings have implications for those who are directly or indirectly concerned with determining the relative effectiveness of traditional and non-traditional vocational choices among youths in relation to several variables. Hence, in spite of some limitations, the present study has its worth. However, further research is still needed in this area, taking into account those variables which were not included in the present study. The study may be helpful for psychologists, teachers, career counselors, and policymakers in understanding the psychological needs of youth while making vocational choices. It also highlights the importance of career guidance and counseling programs that focus not only on employment opportunities but also on psychological readiness and personal development.

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